

Comparative Evaluation of Terrain Characteristics from SRTM and Aster Dems in South East Nigeria

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Abstract-

This study has clearly demonstrated that the results obtained from the different global available DEMs are not the same. In South Eastern Nigeria, this study has shown that ASTER performed better than SRTM modeling the Elevation of the study area, While SRTM performed better at hydrological modeling in the study area. The result shows that SRTM and ASTER GDEM can be used for hydrological modeling and Elevation modeling in the study area respectively. SRTM have shown to be a better DEM for hydrological modeling. The sub catchments delineated from SRTM compares favorably with that of the ALOS PALSAR DEM. The stream network delineated from SRTM is closely related to that obtained from the reference DEM. With the non-availability of up-to-date topographic map of the study area, this research work has further demonstrated that global elevation datasets have a good potential for topographical and hydrological modeling.

Keywords: ALOS PALSAR, ASTER, DEM Quality Assessment, Digital Elevation Model (DEM), Elevation Comparison

1. Introduction

A digital elevation model (DEM) consists of terrain elevations for ground positions at regularly spaced horizontal intervals. DEMs can be used, for example, in the generation of three-dimensional graphics displaying terrain slope, aspect, and terrain profiles between selected points. DEMs have become an important source of topographical data for many scientific and engineering uses, such as hydrological and geological studies, infrastructure planning and environmental applications. Where topographical data is unavailable, global coverage elevation data sets, typically DEMs from remotely sensed data can be the main source of information. DEM generation techniques and DEM quality assessment includes applications in difficult environments.

DEM are useful for many purposes, and are an important precondition for many applications. They are particularly useful in regions that are devoid of detailed topographic maps. DEMs have been found useful in many fields of study such as archaeology, as subtle changes due to previous human activity in the sub surface can be inferred on detailed DEMs (Menze et al., 2006), forestry, e.g. height of trees and relation to preferred tree stem size (Simard et al., 2006), hydrology, like deriving drainage network and overland flow areas that contribute to (suspended) sediment loads (Lane et al., 1994) and analysis of glaciers (movement of glaciers using multi temporal DEM's) and glaciated terrains (change of glacier thickness by comparison of multi temporal DEM's) (Bishop et al., 2001). Thus for a whole range of different studies, DEMs that provide a good representation of the terrain, are of utmost importance as a starting point for further analysis.

SRTM and ASTER-derived DEMs are two post-processed elevation datasets that are frequently used for a wide range of applications due to their near-global coverage (Nikolakopoulos and Chrysoulakis, 2006). Dozens of researchers have, over the past few years, carried out a series of global and local assessments of these products.

The Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) 1-arc second DEM (approx. 30m resolution) is the result of a collaborative effort by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA), the National Imagery and Mapping Agency (NIMA), the German Aerospace Centre (DLR), and Italian Space Agency (ASI) (Foni et al., 2004, Jenson et al., 1998 and Sharma et al., 2010). The mission was launched on 11 February 2000 aboard the Space Shuttle Endeavour. Using radar interferometry, a 3-arc second (SRTM-3) DEM was produced covering almost 80% globe excluding polar regions. Initially a 1-arc second data product was also produced, but was not available for all countries. However, since January 2015 NASA is providing the 1-arc second data freely for many countries including India. The data currently is being distributed by NASA/USGS (finished product) contains 'no-data' termed as voids where water or heavy shadow prevented the quantification of elevation. These are generally small holes, which nevertheless render the 'no-data' especially in fields of hydrological modelling. Later, through further processing the original DEMs are

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filled in these no-data voids. SRTM has been the first mission using space-borne interferometric SAR (InSAR). The SRTM mission has been a breakthrough in remote sensing of topography, producing the most complete, highest resolution DEM of the world. An extensive global assessment revealed that the data meets and exceeds the mission's 16m (90%) absolute height accuracy, often by a factor of two.

The Advanced Spaceborne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer (ASTER) is an advanced multispectral imager that was launched onboard NASA's Terra spacecraft in December, 1999. ASTER has three spectral bands in the visible near-infrared (VNIR), six bands in the shortwave infrared (SWIR), and five bands in the thermal infrared (TIR) regions, with 15-, 30-, and 90-m ground resolution, respectively (Yamaguchi et al. 1998). The VNIR subsystem has one backward-viewing (27.70 off-nadir) instrument for stereoscopic observation in the along-track direction, making imagery acquired by this satellite suitable for DEM generation. The ASTER GDEM, made available in June 2009, was generated using stereo-pair image collected by the ASTER instrument onboard Terra. ASTER GDEM coverage spans from 83° north latitudes to 83° South, encompassing 99 percent of Earth's landmass. It has an along-track stereoscopic capability using its near infrared spectral band and its nadir-viewing and backward viewing telescope to acquire stereo image data with a base-to-height ratio of 0.6. One nadir-looking ASTER visible and near-infrared (VNIR) scene consists of 4,100 samples by 4,200 lines corresponding about 60 km x 60 km ground area. The accuracies estimated for the ASTER GDEM are 20m for the elevation values and 30m for horizontal positioning. This assessment concluded that the actual elevation accuracy of GDEM tiles is within or close to the stated accuracy of 20 meter at 95% confidence.

Advanced Land Observing Satellite (ALOS) Phased Array L-band SAR (PALSAR) is an active microwave sensor using L-band frequency and has various products of different resolution. PALSAR RTC1 products with a pixel size of 12.5m are generated from high resolution and mid resolution digital elevation models (DEMs). Products cover landmasses generally from 60 degrees' northern latitude to 59 degrees' southern latitude. All RTC products are geocoded to the Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) projection provided in GIS ready GeoTIFF format.

In this study, the SRTM and ASTER – derived DEMs are compared and validated against a reference DEM for the South-Eastern states of Nigeria. For many environmental and hydrological processes, even if the absolute elevation is not correct, relative to its surrounding regions it might for example exhibit the appropriate flow direction which is the basis of many GIS routines to derive a hydrological network. The reference DEM used was ALOS PALSAR of 12.5m resolution.

The most freely available global elevation datasets (SRTM and ASTER GDEM) provide an alternative source of obtaining elevation data for topographic mapping of urban and rural areas for various applications such as hydrology and watershed dynamics, erosion modeling, flooding etc. Although, many applications use SRTM and ASTER products around the world, there is limited scientific literature on their quality and application fitness. SRTM and ASTER DEM contains elevation information of vegetation, buildings and other surface features, and only gives elevation of terrain in areas where there is little or no ground cover. The accuracy of elevation products derived from these DEMs depends on the terrain characteristics and land cover types.

Since, a number of applications rely solely on SRTM and/or ASTER DEM, there is need to assess their quality especially in south eastern Nigeria, that is characterized with several environmental problems such as erosion and flooding. Nikolakopoulos et al (2006) posited that these global elevation datasets are subjected to errors, mainly due to the methodology followed to extract elevation information and the various processing steps the model have undergone (e.g. interpolation). Extensive and systematic evaluation of these datasets requires substantial ground truthing. To adequately evaluate the accuracy of these DEMs, there is need to compare elevation information from these global dataset with higher accuracy elevation dataset at varying terrain characteristics.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study Area

The study area, South East, Nigeria is located within latitudes 4° 47' 35"N and 7° 7' 44"N, and longitudes 7° 54' 26"E and 8° 27' 10"E in the tropical rain forest zone of Nigeria. The area comprises the geographical location of the following States: Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu and Imo. The relative location is bounded in the north west by Kogi and Benue States, in the northeast by Cross River State, in the South by Akwa Ibom and Rivers States and finally in the West by Delta State. The south eastern part of Nigeria is made up of mountainous regions, particularly in Enugu state.

The study area has mean maximum temperature of 27°C and total annual rainfall exceeding 2500mm. There is usually early rainfall in January/February with full commencement of rainy season in March and stopping in November of each year. The dry season lasts between four to five months. The highest rainfall is recorded from July to October with little break in rainfall in August popularly described as “August break”.

The area is well drained. The notable lakes, rivers and streams that are found draining the area in this zone include Rivers Niger, Imo, Nike Lake, Anambra, Idemili, Njaba, Oguta Lake, Nkisi, Ezu, Oji etc.

Figure 1: Map of the Study Area

2.2. Methodology

The data processing for this study was conducted through several systematic stages to ensure accuracy and reliability in the analysis. The stages involved are as follows:

i. Corrections of Digital Elevation Models (DEMs)

The first stage involved correcting the Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) to address any errors or inconsistencies. This process included removing any artifacts and noise that could affect the quality of the DEM data. Techniques such as filtering, interpolation, and void filling were employed to enhance the accuracy of the elevation data.

ii. Elevation Comparison

Once the DEMs were corrected, the next step was to perform a comparative analysis of the elevation data. This involved overlaying different DEM datasets to identify and quantify any discrepancies. Statistical methods and visual inspections were used to assess the differences and ensure the consistency of the elevation measurements.

iii. Slope Creation and Comparison

In this stage, slope maps were generated from the corrected DEMs. The slope creation process involved calculating the gradient of the terrain at each grid cell within the DEM. Following the generation of the slope maps, a comparison

was conducted to evaluate the variations in slope between different DEM datasets. This comparison helped in identifying any anomalies and ensuring the reliability of the slope data.

iv. Delineation of Watersheds

The delineation of watersheds was carried out using the corrected DEMs. This process involved identifying the boundaries of drainage basins and sub-basins within the study area. Advanced hydrological modeling techniques and GIS tools were used to accurately delineate the watersheds, ensuring that the flow directions and catchment areas were correctly represented.

v. Extraction and Comparison of Hydrological Parameters

Hydrological parameters, such as stream networks, flow accumulation, and drainage density, were extracted from the delineated watersheds. These parameters were then compared across different datasets to assess their consistency and accuracy. The comparison involved both quantitative and qualitative analyses to identify any significant differences and to validate the hydrological models used.

vi. Comparison of Results

The final stage involved a comprehensive comparison of all the results obtained from the previous stages. This comparison was aimed at synthesizing the findings and ensuring that the processed data was accurate and reliable. Any discrepancies identified in the earlier stages were addressed, and the overall consistency of the results was evaluated. This stage also included the documentation of the methodologies and results for future reference and validation.

3. Results

3.1. Comparison of Elevations from SRTM, ASTER and ALOS PALSAR

3.1.1. Elevation Modeling from ASTER DEM

The result obtained from elevation modeling with ASTER DEM is displayed in figure 2.

Figure 2: ASTER Elevation

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The result from modeling elevation with ASTER DEM shows the maximum and minimum elevation values as 600m and -48m respectively. This result is shown in table 1.

Table1: ASTER DEM Terrain Elevation

Dataset	Description	Min.	Max
ASTER	Elevation	-48	600
	Slope	0	70.9371109

3.1.2 Elevation Modeling From SRTM

The results obtained from elevation modeling with SRTM, is displayed in figure 3.

Figure 3: SRTM Elevation

The result from modeling elevation with SRTM shows the maximum and minimum elevation values as 597m and 5m respectively. This result is shown in table 2:

Table 2: SRTM Terrain Elevation

Dataset	Description	Min.	Max
SRTM	Elevation	5	597
	Slope	0	45.85367203

3.1.3 Elevation Modeling from ALOS PALSAR

The results obtained from elevation modeling with ALOS PALSAR, is displayed in figure 4.

Figure 4: PALSAR Elevation

The result from modeling elevation with ALOS PALSAR shows the maximum and minimum elevation values as 619m and -14m respectively. This result is shown in table 3

Table 3: ALOS PALSAR Terrain Elevation

Dataset	Description	Min.	Max
PALSAR	Elevation	-14	619
	Slope	0	71.17585754

3.1.4 Comparism of Elevation Modeling From SRTM, ASTER and ALOS PALSAR

The elevation values of SRTM and ASTER are 597 and 600 maximum elevations, 5 and – 48 minimum elevations respectively; compared against PALSAR’s 619 and – 14 maximum and minimum elevation, ASTER had the closest result in maximum elevation, with SRTM underestimating the maximum elevation. SRTM also had the closest result in minimum elevation, with ASTER DEM underestimating the minimum elevation. This is shown in table 5.4

Table 4: Summary of Elevation Values

Dataset	Description	Min.	Max
PALSAR	Elevation	-14	619
SRTM	Elevation	5	597
ASTER	Elevation	-48	600
Difference (PALSAR/SRTM)	Elevation	±19	22
Difference (PALSAR/ASTER)	Elevation	34	19

3.2 Comparism of SLOPE from SRTM, ASTER and ALOS PALSAR

3.2.1 Slope Modeling From SRTM

The result obtained from Slope modeling with SRTM is displayed in figure 5

Figure5: SRTM Slope

The result from modeling elevation with SRTM shows the maximum and minimum slope values as 45.85 and 0 respectively. This result is shown in table 5:

Table 5: Slope Values from SRTM

Dataset	Description	Min.	Max
SRTM			
	Slope	0	45.85367203

3.2.2 Slope Modeling from ASTER DEM

The result obtained from Slope modeling with ASTER DEM is displayed in figure 6.

Figure 6: ASTER Slope

The result from modeling elevation with ASTER DEM shows the maximum and minimum slope values as 70.93 and 0 respectively. This result is shown in table 6:

Table 6: Slope Values from ASTER DEM

Dataset	Description	Min.	Max
ASTER			
	Slope	0	70.9371109

3.2.3 Slope Modeling from ALOS PALSAR

The result obtained from Slope modeling with ALOS PALSAR is displayed in figure 7:.

Figure 7: PALSAR Slope

The result from modeling elevation with ALOS PALSAR shows the maximum and minimum slope values as 71.17 and 0 respectively. This result is shown in table 7.

Table 7 Slope Values from ALOS PALSAR

Dataset	Description	Min.	Max
PALSAR			
	Slope	0	71.17585754

3.2.4 Comparison of Slope Modeling From SRTM, ASTER and ALOS PALSAR

The Slope values of SRTM and ASTER are 45.85 and 71.17 maximum slope, 0 and 0 minimum slopes respectively; compared against PALSAR's 70.93 and 0 maximum and minimum elevation, ASTER had the better result in maximum slope with a difference of 0.23 when compared to ALOS PALSAR, SRTM underestimating the maximum slope value and had a difference of 25.322 when compared to ALOS PALSAR. This is shown in table 8

Table 8: Summary of slope Values

Dataset	Description	Min.	Max
PALSAR	Slope	0	71.17585754
SRTM	Slope	0	45.85367203
ASTER	Slope	0	70.9371109
Difference (PALSAR/SRTM)	Slope	-	25.32218551
Difference (PALSAR/ASTER)	Slope	-	0.23874664

3.3 Hydrology Modeling from SRTM, ASTER and ALOS PALSAR

Hydrology involves modeling the flow of water on a surface. When modeling the flow of water, you want to know where the water came from and where it is going, flow direction shows the direction of flow from each cell, and the SRTM like the reference data ALOS PALSAR, showed the flow better than ASTER. This is shown in figure 8a, b and c

Figure 8 (a) ASTER flow direction (b) SRTM Flow direction, (c) ALOS PALSAR flow direction

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3.3.1 Flow Accumulation and drainage networks SRTM, ASTER and ALOS PALSAR

Flow Accumulation calculates accumulated flow as the accumulated weight of all cells flowing into each downslope cell in the output raster. If no weight raster is provided, a weight of 1 is applied to each cell, and the value of cells in the output raster is the number of cells that flow into each cell. Flow accumulation and drainage networks were extracted from SRTM, ASTER and ALOS PALSAR datasets and the results are shown in figure 9a, b and c.

Figure 9 (a) ASTER Drainage Network (b) SRTM Drainage Network, (c) ALOS PALSAR Drainage Network

Table 9: Summary of Drainage Extraction

Stream Order	PALSAR		SRTM		ASTER	
	No. of Stream	Length(km)	No. of Stream	Length (km)	No. of Stream	Length (km)
1	164570	2392.162	33444	1197.494	35351	1265.442
2	72077	1047.343	18304	653.8235	20786	742.4098
3	34137	495.0366	4682	169.1098	4411	159.4086
4	11769	172.3809	1335	48.09963	15	0.499167
5	75	1.115057	-	-	-	-
Total		4108.038107		2068.526554		2167.759528

From the results, although the same flow accumulation threshold (≥ 200000) was used for both DEMs, larger differences appeared during the drainage extraction process. For the drainage network, the catchment area extracted is largest for the Reference DEM, 4108.038107km in length, while the catchment areas of ASTER and SRTM are 2167.759528km and 2068.526554km respectively. While the SRTM better delineated the flow of water, ASTER

produced more streams in length. Previous studies on the comparison between SRTM and ASTER DEMs showed SRTM to be the better DEM, although it was pointed out that ASTER had its merits in certain terrains. The better choice for a DEM is dependent on the terrain in question, and for the South Eastern part of Nigeria, ASTER seems to be the better choice for terrain modeling as it had results closer to that of PALSAR, the reference data, but the SRTM showed the direction of flow a lot better than ASTER, which might make it suitable for hydrological purposes. Although, it is recommended that this assertion be further investigated.

4. Summary and Conclusion

SRTM DEM and ASTER GDEM provides alternative source of elevation data needed for environmental modeling applications such as in hydrology and erosion studies. Before this global data can be used for any specific application, there is need to evaluate their performance. Otherwise, one may be using an inappropriate DEM for an environmental modeling application.

This study has clearly demonstrated that the results obtained from the different global available DEMs are not the same. In South Eastern Nigeria, this study has shown that ASTER performed better than SRTM modeling the Elevation of the study area, While SRTM performed better at hydrological modeling in the study area. The result shows that SRTM and ASTER GDEM can be use for hydrological modeling and Elevation modeling in the study area respectively. SRTM have shown to be a better DEM for hydrological modeling. The sub catchments delineated from SRTM compares favorably with that of the ALOS PALSAR DEM. The stream network delineated from SRTM is closely related to that obtained from the reference DEM. With the non-availability of up-to-date topographic map of the study area, this research work has further demonstrated that global elevation datasets, have a good potential for topographical and hydrological modeling.

Based on the result of the findings from this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Further studies should be carried out on the evaluation of these global elevation datasets as new version of them are released for public use.
2. SRTM should be used for hydrological modeling in South East Nigeria or other areas that have similar topographic configuration like the study area. Also, ASTER DEM Could be used where higher accurate elevation data are not readily available since they can be obtained freely online.

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